

Surface area of Indian Clay Minerals

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A literature survey reveals that a great deal of work has been done on clay minerals of different countries from the point of view of surface area, pore size distribution, carriers and their catalytic activity¹⁻⁷. Indian clay minerals on the other hand have mainly been studied from the point of view of particle size and structure and little work appears to have been done on surface area, pore size distribution and catalytic activity. Hence it has been thought worthwhile to make a systematic study on the Indian mineral clays. This paper, therefore, first presents the surface area of Indian mineral clays which might help us in elucidating the catalytic activity of clay minerals.

Experimental

The surface area of Indian mineral clays have been determined by BET volumetric gas adsorption method which has been described elsewhere⁸.

Adsorbents: Indian clay samples, representative of several of the most common clay minerals types were selected, namely: kaolinite, bentonite, montmorillonite, pyrophyllite, chrysolite, vernaculite and talc. These samples were purchased from the Indian commercial firms.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 summarizes the values of surface area for Indian mineral clays which were calculated from the linear portion (partial pressure, P_e/P_0 , 0.05-0.35) of the BET plot.

TABLE I

Clay minerals	Nitrogen area, V_m sq.m/g.
1. Kaolinite	10.4
2. TALC	20.3
3. Chrysolite	22.1
4. Montmorillonite	38.9
5. Pyrophyllite	49.8
6. Vernaculite	55.3
7. Bentonite	67.7

The surface areas presented in the above table was determined after degassing the clay samples at 200° for 5 hrs. This was done in order to remove the adsorbed water and adsorbed gases from the clay samples. The surface areas were found to have little higher values when compared with the clays of other countries⁹⁻¹¹. The difference may be attributed to the fineness of the clay particles or porous nature of the Indian clays.

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Potentiometric studies of N-benzoylacetone- β -alanine (Schiff base) complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III)

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PROTONATION constants of the Schiff base derived from benzoylacetone and β -alanine, and the formation constants of its complexes with trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically in 50% (vol./vol.) dioxan solutions ($\mu = 0.1M$ NaClO₄) at 30° ± 0.1°. The order of stability constants was found to be La(III) < Ce(III) < Pr(III) < Nd(III). Free energy changes of the complexation reaction have also been evaluated.

The dissociation constants of N-benzoylacetone- β -alanine (abbr. H₂B β A) and the formation constants of its complexes with La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) are reported in this paper.

All the chemicals used were either B.D.H. AnalaR or Riedel reagents. The ligand was synthesised by the method reported earlier¹ and its standard solutions were prepared in dioxan. The metal nitrate solutions were prepared in double distilled water. pH of the solution was measured by employing DORAN pH-meter No. 3078.

Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique²⁻³ as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁴ was adopted for obtaining